

Synthesis of Some Naphtho α - and γ -Pyrones from 2, 7-Dihydroxy Naphthalene

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Several naphtho α - and γ -pyrone derivatives have been synthesised from 2, 7-dihydroxy naphthalene and its 1-formyl and 1,6-diacetyl derivatives through the application of Perkin, Pechmann, Knoevenagel and Kostanecki-Robinson acylation reactions and the structures of the products obtained have been established by chemical and spectral methods.

IN continuation of the work on the synthesis of α - and γ -pyrone derivatives from dihydroxy naphthalenes¹ we have now studied the synthesis of such oxygen heterocycles from 2,7-dihydroxy naphthalene.

2,7-Dihydroxy naphthalene on Pechmann condensation with malic acid in the presence of conc. sulphuric acid afforded 7-hydroxy naphtho (2, 1:6', 5') α -pyrone(I) which was also obtained by Perkin acetylation of the known 2,7-dihydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and hydrolysis of the 7-acetoxy naphtho (2, 1:6', 5') α -pyrone formed. The same product was also obtained from the Knoevenagel condensation of 2,7-dihydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde with diethyl malonate in the presence of piperidine and the hydrolysis and decarboxylation of ethyl-7-hydroxy naphtho (2, 1:6', 5') α -pyrone-3'-carboxylate formed.

2,7-Dihydroxy naphthalene on Pechmann condensation with ethyl acetoacetate in the presence of 80% sulphuric acid gave a product which showed two spots on TLC. A product with melting point 267° was obtained from this which was different from the product obtained by Buu-Hoi and Lavit² on a similar condensation carried out in the presence of hydrogen chloride gas in alcohol. The two products were isomeric α -pyrone derivatives and gave different methyl ethers. They also gave acrylic acid derivatives on heating with alkali in the presence of dimethyl sulphate in acetone solution due to the opening of the α -pyrone ring, which is a diagnostic test for an α -pyrone derivative. The acrylic acid obtained from our product on oxidation gave an acid which had the same melting point as 2,7-dimethoxy-3-naphthoic acid, previously reported by Sunthakar and Gilman³. 7-Hydroxy-4'-methyl-naphtho (2,3:6',5') α -pyrone(III) structure has been assigned to the product with melting point 267° and 7-hydroxy-4'-methyl naphtho (2, 1:6', 5') α -pyrone(II) structure to Buu-Hoi's product (m.p. 276°) on the basis of the NMR data.

2,7-Dihydroxy naphthalene on condensation with ethyl acetoacetate in boiling diphenyl ether gave a product which was soluble in alkali and was different from both, the angular and the linear α -pyrone derivatives, described before. It has been assigned the 7-hydroxy-2'-methyl naphtho (2, 1:6', 5') γ -pyrone(IV) structure. It is known that such a condensation gives γ -pyrone derivatives⁴.

7-Hydroxy-4'-methyl naphtho (2, 3:6', 5') α -pyrone on formylation with hexamine gave a formyl derivative to which the 8-formyl structure has been assigned on the basis of the NMR data. On condensation with diethyl malonate in the presence of piperidine it gave an alkali insoluble product to which ethyl-4'-methyl naphtho (2, 3:6', 5' and 7, 8:6'', 5'') di- α -pyrone-3''-carboxylate(VI) structure is assigned. On hydrolysis and decarboxylation it gave 4'-methyl naphtho (2, 3 : 6', 5' and 7, 8 : 6'', 5'') di- α -pyrone (VI).

1,6-Diacetyl-2,7-dihydroxy naphthalene, prepared according to Kuriakose and Sethna⁵, when subjected to Kostanecki-Robinson benzoylation gave a product which was insoluble in alkali and on the basis of its analysis and IR data (ν_{\max} 1631 cm^{-1} γ -pyronyl >CO, 1645 cm^{-1} benzoyl <CO) has been assigned 2', 2''-diphenyl-3', 3''-dibenzoyl naphtho (2, 1 : 6', 5' and 7, 6 : 6'', 5'') di- γ -pyrone(VII) structure. It could not be debenzoylated either with alcoholic alkali or with sodium carbonate. It has been observed by Bhullar and Venkataraman⁶ that even though the 3-acetyl group in 3-acetyl-chromones can be readily removed by boiling with alkali, 3-acetyl naphtho γ -pyrones are either unaffected or the pyrone ring breaks down on prolonged boiling with alkali.

Experimental

7-Hydroxy naphtho (2, 1 : 6', 5') α -pyrone : A mixture of 2,7-dihydroxy naphthalene (2 g.) malic

acid (4.0 g.) and conc. sulphuric acid (8 ml.) was heated in an oil bath at 110° for 2 hr. The product obtained on pouring the reaction mixture on crushed ice crystallised from diphenyl ether. Yield 0.4 g., m.p. 278°. It was soluble in alkali. (Found : C, 73.64 ; H, 3.67. $C_{18}H_8O_8$ requires C, 73.58 ; H, 3.77%).

7-Acetoxy naphtho (2, 1 ; 6', 5') α -pyrone : A mixture of 2,7-dihydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde (1 g.), fused sodium acetate (3 g.) and acetic anhydride (8 ml.) was refluxed at 170-80° for 12 hr. The product obtained on pouring the reaction mixture in water was washed with dil. alkali. It crystallised from xylene in fine needles (0.4 g.), m.p. 185°. (Found : C, 70.79 ; H, 3.77. $C_{15}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 70.87 ; H, 3.93%).

Hydrolysis : The above acetoxy derivative (0.5 g.) was triturated with cold conc. sulphuric acid (6 ml.) for 10 minutes and poured into ice cold water. The separated product was extracted with dilute alkali. The product obtained on acidification was crystallised from dimethyl formamide in shining plates. M.p. 278°. Mixed m.p. with 7-hydroxy naphtho (2, 1 : 6', 5') α -pyrone was not depressed.

Ethyl-7-hydroxy naphtho (2, 1 : 6', 5') α -pyrone-3-carboxylate : A mixture of 2,7-dihydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde (0.5 g.) diethyl malonate (8 ml.) and

a few drops of piperidine was kept overnight. The reaction mixture was decomposed with ice cold hydrochloric acid. The product obtained crystallised from alcohol in fine greenish yellow needles (0.2 g.), m. p. 237°. (Found : C, 67.74 ; H, 4.11. $C_{18}H_{12}O_8$ requires C, 67.61 ; H, 4.22%).

7-Hydroxy-3'-carboxy naphtho (2, 1 : 6', 5') α -pyrone : The above ester (0.4 g.) was refluxed in glacial acetic acid (75 ml.) with conc. hydrochloric acid (30 ml.) for 4 hr. Product, which separated on pouring the reaction mixture in water was taken up in sodium bicarbonate solution. The product obtained on acidification crystallised from dimethyl formamide. M.p. 312°. Yield 0.2 g. (Found : C, 65.16 ; H, 2.81. $C_{14}H_8O_8$ requires C, 65.62 ; H, 3.12%).

Decarboxylation : The above acid (0.4 g.) was refluxed with copper bronze (0.2 g.) in quinoline (8 ml.) for 45 minutes and filtered. Hydrochloric acid (1:1) was added to the filtrate and the separated product was crystallised from dimethyl formamide. M.p. 278°. Yield 0.15 g. Mixed m.p. with 7-hydroxy naphtho (2, 1 : 6', 5') α -pyrone described above was not depressed.

7-Hydroxy-4'-methyl naphtho (2, 1 : 6', 5') α -pyrone : A cooled solution of 2,7-dihydroxy naphthalene (4 g.) and ethyl acetoacetate (10 ml.) in ethanol (40 ml.) was saturated with hydrochloric acid gas and left for 48 hr. The product obtained crystallised from acetic acid. M.p. 276°. Yield 1.1 g. Bun Hoi and Lavit² reported m.p. 277°. (Found : C, 74.83 ; H, 4.06, $C_{14}H_{10}O_8$ requires C, 74.33 ; H, 4.42%). IR (nujol) ν_{max} , cm^{-1} : 3300 (-OH), 1690 (>CO). UV (Methanol) λ_{max} , nm : 282, 294, 346. NMR (DMSO) δ : 7.86-7.66 (three proton multiplet due to H-3, H-4 and H-5) ; 7.2-6.9 (two proton multiplet due to H-6 and H-8) ; 6.2 (singlet due to H-3').

The methyl ether : Prepared by refluxing a mixture of the above α -pyrone (1 g.) dimethyl sulphate (1.5 ml.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (2 g.) in dry acetone (50 ml.) for 5 hr and crystallised from acetic acid in needles (0.4 g.), m.p. 128°. (Found : C, 74.95 ; H, 4.80. $C_{18}H_{12}O_8$ requires C, 75.18 ; H, 5.00%).

β-Methyl-*β*[1-(2,7-dimethoxy naphthyl)] acrylic acid: The above coumarin (0.2 g.) was refluxed with potassium hydroxide (20%; 10 ml.) and dimethyl sulphate (0.5 ml.) in acetone (20 ml.) for 3 hr. The product obtained on acidification of the alkaline solution crystallised from dilute alcohol in thick needles, m.p. 182°. It decolourises bromine water and dilute potassium permanganate solution. (Found: C, 71.08; H, 5.77. C₁₈H₁₆O₄ requires C, 70.58; H, 5.88%).

7-Hydroxy-4'-methyl naphtho (2,3:6',5')-*α*-pyrone: A mixture of 2,7-dihydroxy naphthalene (2 g.) ethyl acetoacetate (4 ml.) and sulphuric acid (80%; 15 ml.) was kept for 24 hr. The product obtained on pouring the reaction mixture in water crystallised from acetic acid and showed m.p. around 226°. It showed two spots in TLC and was therefore subjected to column chromatography and eluted with methanol. The product obtained on removing the solvent crystallised first from xylene and then from acetic acid and gave a single spot in TLC. M.p. 267°. Yield 0.9 g. Mixed m.p. with 7-hydroxy-4'-methyl naphtho (2,1:6',5') *α*-pyrone described above was depressed by about 40°. (Found: C, 73.85; H, 4.20. C₁₄H₁₀O₃ requires C, 74.33; H, 4.42%). IR (nujol) ν_{\max} , cm⁻¹: 3325 (-OH); 1700 (>CO). UV (Methanol) λ_{\max} , nm: 282, 294, 332. NMR (DMSO) δ : 7.48 (singlet due to H-1), 8.1 (singlet due to H-4), 7.82 (doublet due to H-4, J=9Hz) 7.16 (doublet due to H-6, J=9Hz), 7.1 (singlet due to H-8) and 6.23 (singlet due to H-3').

The methyl ether: Prepared by refluxing the above *α*-pyrone with dimethyl sulphate in dry acetone (75 ml.) as before and crystallised from acetic acid in fine needles (0.5 g.) gave m.p. 220°. (Found: C, 75.43; H, 4.77. C₁₅H₁₂O₃ requires C, 75.13; H, 5.00%).

β-Methyl-*β*[3-(2,7-dimethoxy naphthyl)] acrylic acid: The above *α*-pyrone (0.2 g.) was refluxed with potassium hydroxide (20%; 5 ml.) and dimethyl sulphate (0.5 ml.) in acetone (20 ml.) for 4 hr. The product obtained crystallised from dilute alcohol in thin plates, m.p. 175°. It decolourises bromine water and dilute potassium permanganate solution. Found: C, 70.55; H, 6.06. C₁₈H₁₆O₄ requires C, 70.58; H, 5.88%).

2,7-Dimethoxy-3-naphthoic acid: The above acrylic acid derivative (0.4 g.) was refluxed with potassium permanganate (1.5 g.) and sodium hydroxide (50%; 10 ml.) for 2 hr. More of potassium permanganate

(0.5 g.) was added in small quantity at regular intervals. The reaction mixture was filtered and the filtrate decolourised by adding sodium sulphite solution. The product obtained on acidification crystallised from alcohol in thick needles, m.p. 186°. Sunthakar and Gilman⁸ reported m.p. 185.5°. (Found: C, 67.73; H, 5.00. C₁₈H₁₂O₄ requires C, 67.24; H, 5.17%).

7-Hydroxy-8-formyl-4'-methyl naphtho (2,3:6',5') *α*-pyrone: A mixture of 7-hydroxy-4'-methyl naphtho (2,3:6',5') *α*-pyrone (2 g.) and hexamine (6 g.) in glacial acetic acid (50 ml.) was refluxed for 40 min. Hydrochloric acid (20 ml., 1:1) was then added and the heating continued for further 15 min. The product obtained on dilution of the reaction mixture with water crystallised from acetic acid in shining cream coloured plates (0.7 g.) m.p. 275°. It gave wine red ferric chloride reaction. (Found: C, 70.73; H, 3.77. C₁₅H₁₀O₄ requires C, 70.87; H, 3.93%). NMR (DMSO) δ : 10.61 (singlet due to CHO), 8.57 (singlet due to H-4), 8.11 (singlet due to H-1), 8.1 (doublet due to H-5, J=9Hz) 7.14 (doublet due to H-6, J=9Hz) 6.31 (singlet due to H-3').

Ethyl-4'-methyl naphtho (2,3:6',5') and 7,8:6',5') di-*α*-pyrone-3'-carboxylate: The above formyl derivative (0.5 g.) was dissolved in diethyl malonate (4 ml.) and piperidine (4 drops) was added. The reaction mixture was kept for 24 hr. and treated with alcohol and hydrochloric acid (1:1). The product after washing with dilute alkali was crystallised from dimethyl formamide in pale yellow shining needles (0.25 g.) m.p. 293°. (Found: C, 68.39; H, 3.97. C₂₀H₁₄O₆ requires C, 68.57; H, 3.99%).

4'-Methyl naphtho (2,3:6',5' and 7,8:6',5') di-*α*-pyrone-3'-carboxylic acid: The above ester (0.5 g.) was refluxed in glacial acetic acid (60 ml.) with conc. hydrochloric acid (30 ml.) for 4 hr. The product obtained crystallised from acetic acid. M.p. 320°. Yield 0.2 g. (Found: C, 66.66; H, 3.00. C₁₈H₁₀O₆ requires C, 67.08; H, 3.10%).

4'-Methyl naphtho (2,3:6',5' and 7,8:6',5') di-*α*-pyrone: The above acid (0.4 g.) in quinoline (10 ml.) and copper bronze (0.3 g.) were refluxed for 45 min. and worked up as before. The product obtained crystallised from dimethyl formamide in fine wooly needles (0.2 g.), m.p. >350°. (Found: C, 73.05; H, 3.37. C₁₇H₁₀O₄ requires C, 73.38; H, 3.59%) IR (nujol) ν_{\max} , cm⁻¹: 1725 and 1710 (two *α*-pyrone >CO). UV (Chloroform) λ_{\max} , nm: 268 and 318.

7-Hydroxy-2'-methyl naphtho (2,1:6',5') *γ*-pyrone: A mixture of 2,7-dihydroxy naphthalene

(2 g.) dissolved in diphenyl ether (15 ml.) and ethyl acetoacetate (4 g.) was gently refluxed for 2 hr. The product obtained crystallised from xylene m.p. 285°. Yield 0.5 g. It was soluble in dilute alkali. (Found : C, 74.67 ; H, 4.33. $C_{14}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 74.33 ; H, 4.42%).

2, 2' Diphenyl-3', 3'-bibenzoyl naphtho (2,1 : 6',5' and 7, 6 : 6'', 5'')-di- γ -pyrone : An intimate mixture of 1, 6-diacetyl-2, 7-dihydroxy naphthalene (1 g.) freshly fused sodium benzoate (3 g.) and benzoic anhydride (7 g.) was heated at 190-200° for 10 hr. The reaction mixture was repeatedly treated with sodium bicarbonate solution and then hot water. The product obtained crystallised from xylene. M.p. 242°. Yield 0.4 g. The product was found to be insoluble in dilute alkali and did not give ferric chloride colouration. (Found : C, 80.30 ; H, 4.07. $C_{42}H_{24}O_6$ requires C, 80.70 ; H, 3.84%).

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